

Comadre Discussions: A Culturally Sensitive Intervention to Improve Gestational Diabetes Outcomes in Hispanic Women

Noemi Barajas, DNP, FNP, RNC-MNN, Maria Matza, PhD, RN, CNS, Penny Weismuller, DrPH, RN

Background

- Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM) affects more than 25 % of Hispanic women in the US
- 15 to 50% of women with GDM will develop Type II Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) within 5 years
- Higher than 25% of Hispanic women suffer from GDM
- Hyperglycemia in pregnancy contributes to poor maternal-fetal outcomes
- Managing GDM varies degrees of success
- Standardized curriculum teaching provided in a given setting may not be culturally appropriate

Purpose

Compare outcomes for participants in a culturally appropriate diabetes class to those in the standard class

Methods

- *Comadre* style teaching sessions were added to standardized protocol
- Groups included 3-4 participants for a total of 3 sessions
- Discussions included healthy eating, physical activity, and challenges to lifestyle change

Culturally Competent Change Theory (CCCT)

Figure 2. Adapted from Kurt Lewin change model (Lewin, 1951) and The Process of Cultural Competence in the Delivery of Health Care Services (Campinha-Bacote, 2002).

Discussion

- CCCT promotes provider/patient rapport and benefit; *Comadre* discussions aid in unfreezing behaviors
- Commonality unified the *Comadres* group
- Culturally competent education is sensitive to patients' need to improve diet, exercise, and adherence
- Understanding the Hispanic woman's experience contributes to successful teaching/learning
- Small, intimate group discussions work better than individual teaching or large classroom settings
- Barriers: lack of transportation/childcare

Limitations

- Small sample size limited generalizations
- Most participants had not delivered so no birth outcome data

Recommendations

- Synchronize prenatal care time with teaching sessions
- Organize support services for patients (transportation, child care, WIC referral)
- Implement satisfaction survey

References/Acknowledgements

References available upon request
nbarajas16@csu.fullerton.edu
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Findings

	Comadres	Non-Participants
Age	M = 27.6, SD 6.2	M = 30.2, SD 3.8
Range Weight Gain	6 – 36 pounds	(-2) – 75 pounds
Mean Weight Gain	14 pounds*	24.3 pounds*
Blood Sugars Mean (SD)	106.4* mg/dL (9.42)	107.7* mg/dL (7.08)
Blood Sugars SD	SD = 9.42*	SD = 7.08*

- *Not statistically significant
- Although blood sugar impact was not significant, less weight gain noted in *Comadres*
- Ongoing data collection of delivery outcomes for mother and infant

Comadres were pleased with small group discussion addition to standard large group classes:

“Easier to ask questions”
 “I get to learn from other mothers”
 “Change is hard. Class helps me stay on track”
 “This will help me keep my whole family healthy”

Practice providers were impressed with culturally appropriate approach and referred other patients for support outside of the project classes